

ASSESSMENT OF SPRINKLER SYSTEM FOR EFFICIENCY USING WATER CONVEYANCE, FIELD APPLICATION, AND IRRIGATION SCHEME APPROACH

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Irrigation; Irrigation Water Quality; Sprinkler System; Water Efficiency; Water Conveyance; Field Water Application; Irrigation Scheme; etc.

Abstract: *The necessity to provide a reliable alternative to natural rainfall for irrigating farms prompted the usefulness of a sprinkler irrigation system in the Agricultural Engineering departmental soil and water research station of the University of Science and Technology Ozoro, Nigeria. The design specifically incorporated a rotating sprinkler system for irrigating a small-sized plot, offering a scientifically sound foundation for effective water scheduling, system assessment, and the reduction of water wastage and runoff, tailored for the cultivation of vegetables and cereal crops. In this research work, the performance of the sprinkler system was assessed for its efficiency using the conveyance, field application, and water scheme values obtained using appropriate irrigation formulas and techniques. Field water efficiency in the station was 49.0% for cassava crops. Water conveyance efficiency of 97.9%, application efficiency of 93.35%, and an irrigation scheme of 91.44 were obtained. These findings contribute valuable insights to the performance of the sprinkler irrigation system, emphasizing its potential application for enhancing agricultural practices and water conservation.*

1. Introduction

Water is a key factor in increasing agricultural production. Approximately 1/4 of water resources are allocated for agricultural purposes. Only half of this is effectively utilized by plants. The remaining water resources are squandered, either through deep percolation into the ground or as evaporation. Excessive irrigation not only leads to reduced crop production and soil fertility degradation but also poses ecological risks, such as waterlogging (Alotaibi *et al.*,

2023). Water from irrigation systems is used to augment that which is obtained from rainfall, soil moisture, and groundwater capillary rise. The amount of rainfall in many parts of the world is insufficient to supply the moisture needs of crops. Currently, only around 8.5% of the cultivated area in Africa - roughly 12.2 million hectares - benefits from irrigation (FAO, 2024). Just 10% of the agricultural output in sub-saharan Africa is produced on irrigated land. Over the past three decades, trends in the

Okolotu G. I.

expansion of irrigated land indicate that, on average, irrigation in Africa has been growing yearly. However, this growth rate started declining in the mid-1980s and is currently low. It's worth noting that this rate of change varies significantly from one country to another across the continent (Binswanger-Mkhize & Savastano, 2017).

Irrigation involves the artificial application of water to the soil to achieve the following objectives: ensuring adequate moisture for the growth of crops, providing insurance for crops during short-duration droughts, mitigating the hazards of soil piping, softening the tillage pan (a dense compact layer), regulating the temperature of the soil and atmosphere to create favorable conditions for plant growth, and eliminating or diluting harmful salts in the soil (Nikolaou *et al.*, 2020). There is a rising apprehension about food security in Africa, particularly in sub-saharan Africa. While the overall global food supply and demand situation appears favorable, there is a forecasted deterioration in food security within sub-saharan Africa. Projections suggest a threefold increase in cereal imports between 1990 and 2020, a demand that the region may struggle to meet financially (Wudil *et al.*, 2022).

Irrigation (also referred to as watering) is the artificial application of water either supplementary or total water application to augment rainfall water. It is the application of engineering principles in controlling and harnessing natural sources of water by construction of wells, dams, reservoirs, *etc.*, to agricultural lands. Other sources of irrigation include; rainfall water, atmospheric water other than rainfall (like dew), snow, waste water, flood, ground water, *etc.* Generally, water storage locations are called reservoirs. They are artificially (built by man) and naturally (built by nature) made reservoirs (Akwenuke *et al.*, 2023). Precipitation is a major source of natural water bodies (Okolotu *et al.*, 2023; Okolotu *et al.* 2024). Irrigation has been a fundamental part of agriculture for over 5,000 years and has been developed by numerous cultures across the world (Wikipedia, 2024). The three main irrigation techniques worldwide are water diversion from water bodies (dams, rivers, oceans, *etc.*), canals channeling of surface water, and groundwater pumping. In this study, groundwater pumping was deployed (figure 2). The percentage of agricultural land irrigated for various locations is presented in the figure one (1) below;

Okolotu G. I.

Figure 1: Percentage of agricultural land irrigated (Wikipedia, 2024)

Irrigation Water Quality: Soluble constituent of water are magnesium, calcium, sodium and potassium as cations while chloride, bicarbonate and carbonates as anions. In minor quantities, lithium, silicon, iodine, bromide, nickel, copper *etc.* These soluble constituent elements in water in terms of total salt concentration do not have major effect on the quality of irrigation. The major problems associated with using poor quality irrigation water include; salinity (if the quantity of salts in irrigated water is high enough for salt accumulation within the root zone of crops, the irrigated field will be affected), toxicity (related to boron, sodium and chloride intake and accumulation from irrigation water by crops resulting to reduced yield), permeability (this

happens when the rate of water infiltration into the soil is reduced as a result of lack of salts in the water due to inadequate supply of water which leads to reduced yield). Excessive vegetation growth, delayed crop maturity, and lodging may result from excessive nitrogen in the irrigated water. Sprinkler-irrigated water with high bicarbonate and un-usual pH content may lead to the deposition of white substance on fruits and leaves as well as cause abnormalities.

Sprinkler irrigation is a pressurized irrigation system that uses a network of pipelines to distribute water to specific sprinkler heads or water applicators in the field. Sprinkler systems are more expensive than most surface systems, but they provide much more flexibility and control. They can be used for cooling and

Okolotu G. I.

frost/freeze protection, and they can save up to 50% of water when compared to other surface irrigation methods. They also increase productivity by roughly 15% to 25% (Sheikhsmæili *et al.*, 2016).

The use of sprinkler irrigation is superior to traditional surface watering. By evenly dispersing water in the form of rain across the land surface when needed in the necessary quantity and pattern, it encourages natural rainfall. To prevent surface runoff from irrigation, water is delivered at a rate lower than the soil's infiltration rate. Sprinkler irrigation systems work well on undulating terrain, in situations when water is scarce, on sandy or shallow soils, and when a consistent water supply is needed (Brennan, 2007). Because the sprinkler approach eliminates the need for ground leveling, it is significantly less expensive. Crops can be cultivated with sprinkling irrigation even on dunes. Sprinkler irrigation is a cost-effective and efficient method of applying fertilizer to plants by distributing it uniformly and controlling the application rate. It also ensures that the fertilizer is administered evenly, preventing waste and reducing costs. Sprinkler

irrigation is ideal for various soil types, especially coarse, sandy, and gravelly soils.

A significant number of the poorest farmers and food-insecure individuals in the developing world rely extensively on root and tuber crops, considering them a substantial, if not the primary, source of food, nutrition, and cash income (Scott, 2021), sprinkler irrigation maximize yields. Owing to its importance in the mass production of agricultural food products, most research work is centered on surface irrigation. On the other hand, little information is available on the design and significance of sprinkler irrigation systems, probably leading to the underutilization of irrigation systems. With the recent campaign by the federal government for the development of the non-oil sector of the Nigerian economy and the ban on importation of foreign rice (around year 2020) and other agricultural products, this research is a step in the right direction, as it will contribute to the improvement of the gross national product (GNP). A typical example of the sprinkler system is the functional sprinkler irrigation system used in this research and the reservoir source. These are presented in the figure two (2) below;

Okolotu G. I.

I. Sprinkler Source

II. Sprinkler Head And System

Figure 2: Sprinkler irrigation source and reservoir, and irrigation sprinkler head and system (photograph at the station: DSUST)

Water Efficiency: In Europe, agriculture uses about 32% of all the water extracted; however, in the Mediterranean region, this percentage rises to 80% or more (EU, Climate Adapt, 2024). No irrigation system can provide water with 100% efficiency (Kranz, 2024). Meeting a good water efficiency rate for the farmlands and crops is a mark of a good irrigation system. Water efficiency in the farmland is influenced by percolation and soil depth texture. The percolation technique aids the crops to get water into their root zones. Soil depth texture enhances evapotranspiration, and evaporation, and

ensures that fertilizers and essential minerals get into the soil properly.

2. Materials

The materials used in the actualization of this research are presented below;

The Study Area: The 400 m² designated research area was used for this study assessment. This location is inside the department of Agricultural Engineering's irrigation research field at Delta State University Of Science And Technology, Ozoro, having a latitude of 5.5447° N, and 6.2323° E. Ozoro is a growing town sited in Delta State – Nigeria, West Africa, having slightly flat topography. The location is presented in figure three (3) below;

Okolotu G. I.

I. Map Of Ozoro

II. Ozoro neighboring towns to southern Atlantic ocean

Figure 3: Map location of the study area, and its neighbouring towns to the southern Atlantic ocean

Other materials used include: Measuring tape, marking out tools (Engineering chalks and marker), hand gloves, pumping machine, water reservoir, water gauge, cassava plants, etc.

3. Methods

Upon pumping of 2000 litres of water into the overhead PVC water tank, irrigation water was release from the overhead tank by opening the ball clock which leads into the main pipe connected to the sprinkler nozzles via the laterals, enabling the sprinklers to start sprinkling water as expected. Irrigation water efficiencies were obtained using the site methods. Field water efficiency (%) was obtained following Wikipedia, (2024) formula below;

$$FWE = (Cwt \div Fwa) \times 100 \quad (Eq.1)$$

Where:

FWE = Field water efficiency

Cwt = Water transpired by crop

Fwa = Water Applied to field

Water conveyance efficiency was calculated using the equation below in line with Howell, (2003) as below;

$$Ec = (Wl \div Wr) \times (100) \quad (Eq. 2)$$

Where:

Ec = Water conveyance efficiency

Wl = Volume of water applied to land

Wr = Volume of water taken from the reservoir

The computations are presented in table one (1) below;

Table 1: Water conveyance efficiency

Okolotu G. I.

S/N	Volume of water applied to land, Wl	Volume of water taken from the reservoir, Wr	Water conveyance efficiency, Ec
1	582	600	97.0
2	587	600	97.8
3	594	600	99.0
Av.	587.7	600	97.9

Water application efficiency was computed using the water formula in accordance to Kranz, (2024) below;

$$E_a = (d_s \div d_p) \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

Where:

E_a = Water application efficiency

d_s = Depth of water stored in the root zone (inches)

d_p = Depth of water pumped (inches).

Also;

$$d_s = D_{air} - D_{bir} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

Where:

d_s = Depth of water stored in the root zone
 D_{air} = depth after irrigation reading

Table 2: Depth of water stored in root zone computation

S/N	Depth Before Irrigation Reading, D_{bir}	Depth After Irrigation Reading, D_{air}	Depth Of Water Stored In Root Zone, $d_s = D_{air} - D_{bir}$
1	1.77	2.24	0.47
2	1.29	1.81	0.54
3	1.50	2.01	0.51
Av.	1.52	2.02	0.51

Depth of water pumped (d_p) was obtained as below;

$$d_p = (Q \times t) \div (A_i \times C) \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

Where:

Q = flow rate

t = time

A_i = area irrigated

C = constant equivalent to 2715.

Okolotu G. I.

231 cubic is approximately 3.785 liters for liquid, thus 86 liters divided by 3.785 liters to give 22.72gal/min for flow rate. Also, the acre is 4046.86 square meters, and the 400m irrigation

area is 400m / 4046.86 which yields 0.0988, by an approximation of 0.10 acre below for the area irrigated. The computations are presented in table three (3) below;

Table 3: Water application efficiency computation

S/N	Depth of water stored in root zone, Ds (inches)	Flow rate, Fr (in gal/min)	Time, T (in minutes)	Area irrigated, Ai (in acres)	Constant (in gal/acin)	Depth of water pumped, dp (in inches)	Water Application, Ea (in %)
1	0.47	22.72	65	0.10	27154	0.5439	87.04
2	0.54	22.72	65	0.10	27154	0.5439	99.28
3	0.51	22.72	65	0.10	27154	0.5439	93.77
Av	0.51	22.72	65	0.10	27154	0.5439	93.36

The formula can be used to compute the scheme irrigation efficiency (e) once the conveyance and field application efficiency have been established below;

$$e = (ec \times ea) \div 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Where:

e = Scheme irrigation efficiency (%)

Table 4: Efficiency results

S/N	Field water efficiency, Efw	Conveyance efficiency, Ec	Field application efficiency, Ea	Scheme irrigation efficiency, Is
1	470	97.0	87.0	84.39
2	480	97.8	99.28	97.10
3	520	99.0	93.77	92.83
Av.	490	97.9	93.35	91.44

The results of efficiency curve from various experimentations are presented in figures four to six (4-6) below;

Okolotu G. I.

Figure 4: First efficiency curve

Figure 5: Second efficiency curve

Figure 6: Third efficiency curve

5. Discussion

The assessment of the sprinklers were centered on the irrigation scheme which possesses the required efficiency variables. Irrigation scheme efficiency ratings include; 20% - 30% (poor), 40% (reasonable), and 50% - 60% (good). These values are the globally incorporated range for a scheme of irrigation work. FAO, (2024) noted that these values are only indicative values. Thus, these values are checkmates to the site-obtained values.

Water efficiency in the station was 470, 480, and 520 for the three tests on cassava crops. The results were within range for the relative crop efficiency results of Wikipedia, (2024), and the following crops were identified by (FAO-NRMED, 2022) as having an approximate water requirement for seasonal crops: sugar cane (1500–2500), bananas (1200–2200), citrus (900–1200), potatoes (500–700), tomatoes (400–800), barley/oats/wheat (450–650),

cabbage (350–500), onions (350–550), and peas (350–500).

For optimal performance of the irrigation system, ensuring a regular maintenance schedule on the irrigation system is vital. This will extend the useful lifespan of the irrigation system, ensure operational readiness of the irrigation system, avoid exorbitant expenses on the repairs of the irrigation system, and ensure the safety of the users.

The closest considerable choice of the assessed sprinklers (in the study area) is the drip system, an additional channel watering technique. A drip irrigation system uses drip pipes to provide irrigation water straight to the plant. Drip irrigation, also known as trickling irrigation, is a technique where water is slowly dripped into the soil at very low rates (0.2 to 2.0 liters/hour) using a network of plastic pipes with small diameters and emitters or drippers as the outputs (FAO, 2023). Water is applied to the

Okolotu G. I.

root zone one drop at a time using drip emitters in drip irrigation (Hossain *et al.*, 2023). As a result, less water is wasted. The emitters have extremely tiny canals, with diameters between 0.2 to 2.0 mm (FAO, 2023). The tiny diameter of the waterway makes it easy to obstruct the emittent.

6. Conclusion

Field water efficiency of 490 and Irrigation scheme rating of 91.44 in the station are good. Prior results obtained and discussed, it was concluded that the efficiency was in good order. The irrigation facility was installed for small - sized plot of vegetables due to their high consumptive rate and shallow root system. Thus, the irrigation facility meets the ideal requirements of its intended crops and field.

Abbreviations

Table 5: words coded and their decodings

S/N	Code	Decode
1	FWE	Field water efficiency
2	Cwt	Water transpired by crop
3	Fwa	Water applied to field
4	Ec	Water conveyance efficiency
5	Wl	Volume of water applied to land
6	Wr	Volume of water taken from the reservoir
7	Ea	Water application efficiency
8	ds	Depth of water stored in the root zone
9	dp	Depth of water pumped
10	Dair	Depth after irrigation reading
11	Dbir	Depth before irrigation reading.
12	Q	Flow rate
13	t	Time
14	Ai	Area irrigated
15	C	Constant equivalent
16	e	Scheme irrigation efficiency
17	ec	Conveyance efficiency
18	ea	Field application efficiency

Okolotu G. I.

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Data Availability Statement

All raw data used were generated prior the field study. No secondary data was used.

Conflicts of Interest

No conflicts of interest of any sought.

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Okolotu G. I.